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KEY POINTS OF EPIDEMIOLOGY AND PATHOGENESIS, MODERN CONCEPT OF DIAGNOSIS AND DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS OF VARIOUS MORPHOLOGICAL VARIANTS OF NODULAR GOITER

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Annotation. *Unified classifications of ultrasound and cytological diagnosis of nodular goiter are demonstrated. Methods for optimizing radical treatment are considered. The guidelines are provided with supporting material, an algorithm for diagnosing and managing patients. Recommended for endocrinologists, ultrasound specialists, clinical laboratory diagnostic specialists, radiologists, surgeons, general practitioners.*

Key words: *thyroid gland, nodular goiter, nodular colloid goiter, thyroid cancer, ultrasound, fine-needle aspiration biopsy, TIRADS classification, Bethesda classification.*

**КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ ПОЛОЖЕНИЯ ЭПИДЕМИОЛОГИИ И ПАТОГЕНЕЗА,
СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ПРЕДСТАВЛЕНИЯ О ДИАГНОСТИКЕ И
ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНОЙ ДИАГНОСТИКЕ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ
МОРФОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ВАРИАНТОВ УЗЛОВОГО ЗОБА.**

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Аннотация. Приведены унифицированные классификации ультразвуковой и цитологической диагностики узлового зоба. Рассмотрены методы оптимизации радикального лечения. Рекомендации снабжены вспомогательным материалом, алгоритмом диагностики и ведения пациентов. Рекомендуется эндокринологам, специалистам УЗИ, специалистам клинической лабораторной диагностики, рентгенологам, хирургам, врачам общей практики.

Ключевые слова: щитовидная железа, узловой зоб, узловой коллоидный зоб, рак щитовидной железы, УЗИ, тонкоигольная аспирационная биопсия, классификация TIRADS, классификация Bethesda.

Section 1. Epidemiology, etiology and pathogenesis Among the population, during palpation of the thyroid gland, nodular goiter is recorded in 3–5% of subjects, in 20–35% during screening ultrasound examination (US) and tissue autopsy tissue thyroid nodules are detected in more than 50% of cases. There are many etiological factors for the development of nodular nontoxic goiter (goitrogens, defect in the synthesis of thyroid hormones), but the most common cause of its development is iodine deficiency. Diffuse endemic goiter and UKZ are included in the spectrum of iodine deficiency diseases.

According to epidemiological studies conducted by the Federal Endocrinological Research Center, there are no territories in the Russian Federation where the population is not at risk of developing iodine deficiency diseases. The prevalence of iodine deficiency thyropathies in different regions of Russia varies from 5.2 to 70% and the national average is 31%. Women develop goiter 2–3 times more often than men. Among children, the highest incidence of diffuse nontoxic goiter and UKZ is characteristic of adolescence.

In the early stages of goiter development (usually in children, adolescents and young adults), compensatory hypertrophy of thyrocytes occurs.

The formation of nodular formations in the thyroid gland is regarded as involution of the organ against the background of diffuse endemic goiter in conditions of chronic iodine deficiency.

There is no doubt that all adaptation reactions are stimulated and controlled by thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH). However, as shown in many studies, the TSH level does not increase in diffuse endemic goiter. In the course of a number of in vivo and in vitro studies, new data were obtained on the autoregulation of the thyroid gland by iodine and autocrine growth factors, such as insulin-like growth factor type 1, epidermal growth factor and fibroblast growth factor, which, under conditions of decreased content iodine in the thyroid gland has a powerful stimulating effect on thyrocytes. It was experimentally demonstrated that when potassium iodide was added to the culture of thyrocytes, a decrease in TSH-induced, cAMP (cyclic adenosine monophosphate)-mediated mRNA expression by insulin-like growth factor type 1 was observed, with its complete cessation with a significant increase in the potassium dose. iodide.

It is well known that iodine itself not only serves substrate for the synthesis of thyroid hormones, but also regulates the growth and function of the thyroid gland. Thyrocyte proliferation is inversely related to intrathyroidal iodine content. High doses of iodine inhibit iodine absorption, its organization, synthesis and secretion of thyroid hormones, and absorption of glucose and amino acids. Iodine, entering the thyrocyte, interacts not only with tyrosyl residues in thyroglobulin, but also with lipids. The resulting compounds (iodolactones and iodaldehydes) serve as the main physiological blockers of the production of autocrine growth factors. In conditions of chronic iodine deficiency, there is a decrease in the formation of iodine lipids - substances that inhibit the proliferative effects of autocrine growth factors.

Thyrocytes initially have different proliferation tive activity, i.e. microheterogeneity. Some pools of thyrocytes more actively take up iodine,

others quickly proliferate, and others have low functional and proliferative activity. Under conditions of iodine deficiency, microheterogeneity of thyrocytes becomes pathological: thyrocytes with the greatest ability to proliferate respond to hyperstimulation to a greater extent. Thus, nodular and multinodular euthyroid goiter is formed. As a result of the accumulation of a number of somatic mutations in areas of nodular/multinodular goiter, over time, a number of patients develop functional autonomy (FA) of the thyroid gland. As the volume of autonomously functioning tissue increases, there is a decrease in iodine uptake by the surrounding thyroid tissue, a gradual suppression of TSH secretion and the development of decompensated FA with thyrotoxicosis.

UKZ accounts for the majority (75–90%) of all thyroid nodules. Thyroid FA is the most common cause of thyrotoxicosis in old age and the second most common cause of thyrotoxicosis syndrome in general. With compensated FA, thyrotoxicosis develops in approximately 5% of patients per year.

Section 2. Diagnosis of nodular goiter

2.1. Complaints, anamnesis, clinical examination

Non-toxic goiter of small size is usually asymptomatic. As a rule, goiter is an incidental finding. In the overwhelming majority of cases, under conditions of mild and moderate iodine deficiency, palpable changes in the thyroid gland are detected only with targeted stimulation following.

In conditions of moderate and severe iodine deficiency, goiter can reach large sizes and cause the development of compression syndrome with complaints of difficulty breathing and swallowing, as well as a cosmetic defect in the neck.

In case of long-term goiter (more than 10–15 years), it is necessary to exclude the presence of thyroid FA, which is one of the main reasons for the development of thyrotoxicosis in iodine-deficient regions.

Complaints regarding PA are determined by the degree of its compensation. In euthyroidism and subclinical thyrotoxicosis, FA may not manifest itself clinically and is also a random finding. Manifest thyrotoxicosis in FA often proceeds atypically, usually manifesting itself in complaints of cardiac arrhythmias.

The medical history should necessarily take into account the patient's region of residence, family history of thyroid diseases, dietary patterns, and use of iodine-containing medications.

A clinical (physical) examination of a patient with nodular goiter should include an assessment of local signs (voice changes, dysphagia, vocal cord paralysis, etc.), signs of thyroid dysfunction, medical history of interventions on

the thyroid gland, family history, including the presence of nodular goiter and medullary cancer in relatives, previous irradiation of the head and neck area, living in conditions of iodine deficiency. Palpation reveals nodes, usually more than 1 cm.

With retrosternal nodular/multinodular goiter and large goiter, deformation of the neck may be observed, and sometimes, due to compression syndrome, swelling of the neck veins. To assess the degree of thyroid enlargement by palpation, the World Health Organization - WHO (2001) recommends the following classification:

- 0 th (zero) degree – no goiter (the volume of each lobe does not exceed the volume of the distal phalanx of the subject’s thumb);
- 1st degree – the goiter is palpable, but not visible when the neck is in normal position. This also includes nodular formations that do not lead to enlargement of the gland itself;
- 2nd degree – the goiter is clearly visible in the normal position of the neck

It is important to note that the dimensions of the thyroid gland determined by palpation do not always coincide with the true ones, for example, due to the low location of the thyroid gland itself or the substernal goiter. Palpation of the thyroid gland should be accompanied by palpation examination of the cervical lymph nodes.

The characteristics of the number of nodules are also taken into account:

- nodular goiter is the only encapsulated formation in the thyroid gland (solitary node);
- multinodular goiter – multiple encapsulated nodular formations in the thyroid gland, not fused to each other;
- conglomerate nodular goiter – several encapsulated formations in the thyroid gland, fused to each other and forming a conglomerate;
- diffuse nodular (mixed) goiter – nodes (nodule) against the background of diffuse enlargement of the thyroid gland.

2.2. Laboratory diagnostics

If a thyroid nodule is detected in a patient, determination of the basal TSH level is indicated. If a reduced TSH level is detected, the level of free thyroxine (f. T4) and free triiodothyronine (f. T3) is additionally determined; if an elevated TSH is detected, the level of f. T4.

Determining the level of thyroglobulin, as well as antibodies to the thyroid gland in nodular goiter at the initial stage of diagnosis is not indicated. For

differential diagnosis of thyrotoxicosis syndrome, determination of antibodies to the TSH receptor is indicated.

To confidently exclude medullary cancer, it is recommended to determine the level of basal calcitonin; it is indicated for nodular goiter in children, adolescents, young people, with a family history of medullary cancer, suspicious ultrasound (US) characteristics of a nodular formation in terms of malignancy. - natural risk.

2.3. Instrumental diagnostics

Ultrasound is the most common method for visualizing the thyroid gland and its structural pathology. Despite the high sensitivity in detecting thyroid nodules, ultrasound is not a screening method, as it leads to the identification of a huge number of non-palpable incidentalomas. This approach is not justified either from a medical or economic point of view.

An absolute indication for ultrasound is a change in the thyroid gland according to palpation and/or functional disorders of the thyroid gland according to hormonal examination, as well as a history of radiation therapy to the head and neck, a family history of thyroid cancer, and enlarged regional lymph nodes of unknown origin.

TIRADS classification. The main task of ultrasound in nodular goiter is to determine the indications for fine-needle aspiration biopsy (FNA) and navigation control over its implementation.

The ultrasound protocol should include a description of the location and size of the thyroid mass and lymph nodes, taking into account their ultrasound characteristics: structure, echogenicity, contours, presence of additional inclusions.

Since 2009, a new classification system for thyroid nodules depending on malignancy risk stratification - TIRADS (Thyroid imaging reporting and data system for US features of nodules Horvath et al.) has been used in practical healthcare.

In 2011, this classification was modified by Kwak et al. Currently, EU-TIRADS is being increasingly used. This classification reflects the risk of malignancy, expressed as a percentage (see table). The main disadvantages of this approach in everyday clinical practice are subjectivity and direct dependence on the qualifications of the doctor conducting the examination, as well as slight variability in the assessment of ultrasound categories and subcategories of thyroid nodules according to versions of different authors. Therefore, when describing and assessing the ultrasound characteristics of a nodular lesion using the TIRADS

system, there is a possibility of discrepancies, and the use of classification in describing a nodular goiter is not yet standard for most medical institutions. Nevertheless, a unified, reproducible protocol should have significantly changed approaches to further diagnostics, determining the most optimal tactics for a particular thyroid nodule (biopsy or observation).

UKZ belongs to categories TIRADS 2 and TIRADS 3 (groups of minimal risk of malignancy).

In 2017, a committee of the American College of Radiologists (ACR) formulated its own risk stratification system, a continuation of earlier guidelines. The new system was created to locate knowledge of the most clinically significant thyroid tumors in terms of malignancy, as well as to reduce the number of biopsies on benign nodes.

This technique evaluates such ultrasound signs as structure, echogenicity, contours, shapes, echogenic inclusions. Each symptom, depending on its severity, is assigned points from 0 to 3.

The totality of points determines the probability of malignant lesion of the thyroid formation:

- TR1 – benign – 0 points;
- TR2 – no suspicion of malignancy – 2 points;
- TR3 – slight suspicion of malignancy – 3 points;
- TR4 – moderate suspicion of malignancy – 4–6 points;
- TR5 – serious suspicion of malignancy – 7 points or higher.

Disputable in the updated ACR classification is the exclusion of all nodular formations from the TIRADS 2 category in the indications for FNA.

Fine-needle aspiration (puncture) biopsy FNA is the main method for the differential diagnosis of benign and malignant tumors.

According to numerous studies, the sensitivity and specificity of FNA is very high, and when detecting colloid goiter and papillary thyroid cancer reaches 98–100%. The procedure must be carried out under ultrasound control by a qualified doctor of any specialty (endocrinologist, endocrine surgeon, oncologist, radiology doctor). Carrying out TAB does not require hospitalization or special preparation of the patient. In some cases, TAB in children may require the use of various types of anesthesia, and preliminary consultation with an anesthesiologist and a lawyer is necessary.

- family history of medullary thyroid cancer;
- vocal fold paralysis;

– thyroid nodules accidentally detected during positron emission tomography;

– patient age under 20 years;

– when there is a change in the ultrasound structure of benign thyroid nodes (during dynamic observation) or the appearance of enlarged or changed cervical lymph nodes.

For formations less than 1 cm, if the patient is not at risk for aggressive forms of thyroid cancer, performing FNA is not advisable, regardless of the ultrasound characteristics of the thyroid nodule, except for patients under 20 years of age.

An increase in the size of a benign nodular formation in itself in most cases is not an indication for repeat TAB.

FNA is considered a method of primary morphological diagnosis, but not a method of dynamic observation for cytologically verified benign thyroid nodules.

If a benign cytological conclusion is received from a node with obvious suspicious ultrasound signs, FNA must be repeated as soon as possible.

For cystic anechoic nodes, regardless of size, FNA has no diagnostic value, but can be performed for the therapeutic purpose of evacuating fluid and eliminating a cosmetic defect or compression syndrome of surrounding organs formalized consent to invasive intervention from the child's parents.

TAB does not have any significant complications. Rare complications include subcutaneous hematomas, hemorrhages in the area of the node and local pain that persists for a short time.

Indications for TAB. • thyroid nodules equal to or exceeding 1 cm in diameter (probably, with the introduction of the TIRADS classification into practical healthcare, indications for puncture will be determined depending on the ultrasound characteristics of the nodules);

Cytological examination of the material obtained during TAB

The conclusion of a cytological study should contain a cytological diagnosis, which will allow the clinician to make a clinical diagnosis and determine the optimal treatment tactics for each specific patient. The most effective use of 6 standard categories of conclusions of the modern international cytological classification Bethesda (The Bethesda System For Reporting Thyroid Cytopathology, TBSRTC 2009, revision 2017):

- Category I – non-informative puncture;
- Category II – benign formation;
- Category III – atypia of uncertain significance;

- Category IV – follicular neoplasia or suspected follicular neoplasia;
- Category V – suspicion of malignancy;
- Category VI – malignant formation.

Conclusions containing only a descriptive part, as well as conclusions without a specific cytological diagnosis (“no atypical cells found,” “no data on cancer,” etc.) are regarded as uninformative. In these situations, it is necessary to consult ready-made cytological preparations with another independent morphologist or repeat FNA in a specialized medical institution.

UKZ belongs to category II (benign formations) with a low risk of malignancy (0–3%); rice. 5.

Cytological features of UKZ include the presence of colloid of different densities and in different quantities and follicular cells of polymorphic sizes, often in the form of monolayer clusters. Depending on the degree of proliferation of thyrocytes, UKZ is characterized as a predominantly colloid goiter without proliferation, partially or to varying degrees proliferating and actively proliferating.

With an actively proliferating goiter, the formation of adenomatous and papillary structures is possible, complicating the differential diagnosis. With long-term existing goiter, the smear always contains

There are various secondary background changes - sclerosis, hyalinosis, cystic degeneration, signs of hemorrhage, etc. The severity of degenerative changes can also, in some cases, be the reason for difficult interpretation of FNA data and classification of cell changes into category III (atypia of undetermined significance); rice. 6, which requires a repeat procedure after 1–3 months.

In the presence of thyrotoxic goiter, the smear may show cytological signs of increased functional activity, including large thyrocytes with abundant light cytoplasm and light marginal vacuoles with pink granularity (“flaming cells”).

According to J. Hamburger’s rule, the benignity of a nodular formation can be verified if at least 6 cell clusters are determined in two preparations obtained from different aspirations, each of which contains at least 10–15 “benign” follicular cells. But there are also less stringent criteria that allow for taking only one smear and the presence of at least 3-4 clusters of benign cells with abundant colloid.

Radioisotope scanning

Nodular goiter.

It is carried out for nodular goiter with subclinical or manifest thyrotoxicosis for the differential diagnosis of FA and other causes of

thyrotoxicosis. It is not informative for the primary diagnosis of nodular goiter (for detecting nodes and assessing their size) or nodular colloid non-toxic goiter, as well as for the primary diagnosis of thyroid tumors. Another indication for scanning is thyroid ectopia, which is usually detected in early childhood.

Computed tomography

Nontoxic Multinodular Goiter

It is carried out in case of a large goiter and/or its retrosternal location to assess tracheal compression syndrome.

X-ray of the neck organs with contrast of the esophagus and magnetic resonance imaging are less informative methods.

Differential diagnosis

Differential diagnosis of UKZ is carried out with follicular adenoma, autoimmune thyroiditis with the formation of false nodes, solitary cyst, various forms of thyroid cancer, as well as with various non-thyroid diseases (median neck cyst, lipoma, thymoma, parathyroid adenoma, etc.). d.).

Prospects for the development of diagnostics of nodular goiter

Currently, research work is being carried out to study immunomorphological and molecular genetic markers in the diagnosis of thyroid nodules. The purpose of the research is to determine additional criteria for the differential diagnosis of tumor and non-tumor diseases of the thyroid gland; and also in UKZ - establishing predictors of growth and FA of nodular formations in the early stages of diagnosis.

Indications for consultation with specialists

In case of compression syndrome, consultation with a surgeon is necessary. If thyrotoxicosis is present, consult a radiologist; if there are contraindications to radioiodine therapy, consult a surgeon. With the development of thyrotoxic heart syndrome and in preparation for surgical treatment, consultation with a cardiologist is necessary.

Section 3. Treatment of nodular colloid goiter

There are no conservative treatment methods for UCD. For most patients with UKZ, in the absence of thyroid dysfunction, cosmetic defect and compartment syndrome, dynamic monitoring is recommended: TSH determination once every 12 months, thyroid ultrasound monitoring once every 12 months or less often.

The goal of radical treatment (surgical treatment, radioiodine therapy) is to eliminate compression syndrome, cosmetic neck deformity, and normalize the functional state of the thyroid gland.

Surgical treatment.

Surgical treatment is indicated for nodular (multi-nodular) goiter with signs of compression of surrounding organs and/or a cosmetic defect, detected by decompensated FA. If there are changes in both lobes, the operation of choice is thyroidectomy or extremely subtotal resection, since with organ-sparing operations the risk of recurrence of nodular goiter is 50–80%.

Minimally invasive methods of treating UKZ

Includes percutaneous administration of sclerosants, cryodestruction, laser destruction, diathermocoagulation of the node.

Indications for minimally invasive interventions are extremely limited. They can be used as a method of choice when the necessary radical treatment is associated with a high degree of risk for concomitant diseases, and as an alternative to surgery for UKZ with a cosmetic defect and uninodular toxic goiter. The goal of these methods should be to eliminate the symptom caused by the dominant node.

Any minimally invasive intervention, along with organ-preserving operations, is a symptomatic procedure. Achieving complete node regression is not necessary.

Radioiodine therapy. It is the method of choice for the development of thyrotoxicosis (decompensated FA thyroid gland). Contraindicated during pregnancy.

Indications for hospitalization.

As a rule, hospitalization is not indicated, except in cases of large vascular disease with compression syndrome or severe thyrotoxicosis.

As a rule, patients with nodular goiter, including after surgical treatment, do not require special rehabilitation measures. The exception is patients with a high risk of surgical complications due to damage to the vocal nerve and parathyroid glands.

Section 4. prevention

For both primary and secondary prevention of iodine deficiency diseases, including nodular/multiple goiter colloidal goiter, it is necessary to introduce state preventive programs. Universal salt iodization is recommended by WHO as a universal, highly effective method of population iodine prophylaxis. In groups at increased risk of developing iodine deficiency diseases (pregnant and lactating women, children under 2 years old) living in areas with iodine deficiency, additional intake of iodine preparations (potassium iodide) is required. The goal

of preventive measures is to achieve an optimal constant level of iodine consumption by the population.

Recommended standards for iodine intake developed by WHO depend on age and physiological characteristics and are: 90 mcg/day for children from 0 to 59 months, 120 mcg/day for children 6–12 years old, 150 mcg/day for under-18s and adults, 250 mcg/day for pregnant and lactating women.

For early diagnosis of aggressive forms of thyroid cancer, monitoring is necessary for patients with a history of irradiation of the head and neck and genetic studies in families burdened by the presence of medullary thyroid cancer.

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